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Informal Sector and Urban Planning in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study seeks to examine the effect of informal sector activities on urban planning in Akwa Ibom State. Majorly, open interview method was used of which both government agencies and the informal sector operators were interviewed. Some of the opinions expressed by the two sets of respondents coincided. The goals of the study were to evaluate the urban planning implications of the location and growth of informal sector activities in Akwa Ibom State, the challenges informal sector activities pose on urban planning control and system in Akwa Ibom State, and to ascertain whether urban planners do consider informal sector activities in the urban planning process in Akwa Ibom State. Data were from 2,000 respondents and the findings revealed that due to poor funding and lack of qualified human resource, the Ministry of Lands, Survey and Town Planning and the local government's works department had not been able to do much in terms of urban planning, management, and the regulation of informal activities. The study concludes that the capacity of the informal sector economy to provide employment to the teeming urban population cannot be underscored. However, the sector poses a considerable challenge to urban planners not only in the State considered, but also in other States of the federation on how to integrate them into the urban system. The environmental and public health challenges that they pose have been left unaddressed by planners and other stakeholders. It is therefore, recommended (amongst others) that the government should address the informal sector needs in providing access to infrastructures such as power, water, safety, waste collection and disposal; sanitary facilities and security and make less the cumbersome forms of registration of informal activities.

Keywords: Informal Sector, Urban Planning, Environmental and Land Use Planning and Management

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1.0 Introduction

The unlimited supply of labour theory as developed by Arthur W. Lewis was a theoretical model of economic development based on the assumption that in most developing countries, there were over supply of labour in the traditional sector which consisted of the informal economy such as the petty traders, small-scale producers and a range of other casual or petty jobs; and that this vast pool of surplus labour would be absorbed in the modern industrial sector as the countries grew, after which the informal sector would fade. Unfortunately, a large number of these economically active populations could not find themselves in the modern industrial sector of economic activities but finds an income-creating source in areas outside the formal economy or modern industrial sector of the economy. Its activities have rather experienced rapid growth in developing countries which have consequently attracted increasing attention among social development activists and policy makers. The rapid growth of the sector has been attributed to ever increasing unemployment in these countries.

According to ILO (2004), the lack of jobs in the formal sector of the economy as well as the lack of skills in a large part of the labour force, has resulted in the growth of a substantial informal sector in which most workers are in low-paid employment and poor working conditions. The informal economic activities (as reflected by the type of players), are seen to be unrecognized, unrecorded, unprotected, and unregulated by the public authorities and can be said to be confined to marginal economic activities carried on within the economy although may include some profitable enterprises in manufacturing. The sector, nevertheless, may include small scale activities including small enterprises, household enterprises; self-employed sectors such as street vendors, cleaners, shoe-shiners, hawkers, etc. but it is generally characterized by a large number of small-scale production and service activities that are individually or family-owned and labour-intensive. The drive is usually to obtain sufficient income to survive and count on their indigenous resources to create work (Singh, 2000). Many members of the household, including women and children, are involved in these activities and they often work very long hours. It is difficult to estimate the exact size of the sector but there is a general perception that the sector comprises a growing scheme of economic activities. Particularly in less developed countries, 50 percent of the labour force are engaged in the informal economy (Gottdiener and Budd, 2005; Mengistu and Jibat, 2015). The World Bank and Mazhambe, (2017) aver that the sector includes about 70%

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of the population and that it has a wide range areas of informality spatial, environmental, economic, and social comprising business activities, employment, settlements, and markets. Fapo (2018) says that the sector activities are heterogeneous mix, including a wide variety of economic activities that tend to be ignored in normal economic statistical analysis, whereas each of the activity areas has imposing implications for public policy and that, the sector do link up activities with the formal sector of both the national and universal outlook through subcontracting networks and commodity chains as most vendors in the sector sell goods produced by the formal sector such as cigarette, newspapers, electronic goods, clothes and other branded ones. Therefore, the sector proves to be the major mechanism for economic growth and development.

In most developing countries, the sector is said to be the largest source of employment and investment. This is because the sector offers the best opportunity for the upward mobility in lifeline of the poor people and their children (Brown, 2005). These facets are unfortunately ignored by the urban authorities because the sector is seen as a glitch, a basis of disorder, and an impediment to the development of a modern economy. They judge the slums, health risks, insecurity, and exploitation associated with the sector, and hope that like other transitory phases in the path of development, the sector will fade away with time and economic progress. It is also regarded as a non-profit activity, since it does not contribute to the national economy in terms of tax. To most, the sector activities do not respect legal, social, health and quality standards; do not pay taxes and tends to violate the rules of fair competition. These conflicting axioms pose a difficult dilemma for urban planners and tend to buttress the doubts and resentment of official attitudes towards the sector. Studies show that since informal sector activities have no legal status to conduct their business, they are constantly harassed by the authorities (Bhowmik, 1999); hence, their role has not been well perceived. It is marginalized from the development agenda, and has been severely affected by the functioning of macro socioeconomic policies. Improper or lack of policy support has made the sector to be unsecured, which adversely affects the livelihoods of the urban poor. Yet, they are widespread because they provide the urban population with much needed services that neither the municipalities nor the larger retailing outlets provide.

The urban planning tasks posed by informal activities include the use of space without planning approvals, encroachment on access roads, conflicting land uses, non-

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compliance with the relevant planning law on zoning, etc., all because the planning authorities may not have thought so much about the informal sector perspectives and hence, not assumed that they may have high demand for urban land and spaces to lodge their ever-growing sector activities, or offer guidelines to accommodate and regulate their activities to necessitate provision of essential infrastructures to cater for their needs. Whereas the environmental management encounters of the sector include lack of access to basic infrastructure, degradation of the urban environment, and insecurity of life and property. There is therefore, the need for urban planners to understand the valuable contributions of the informal sector activities to the local economy and then integrate them in the spatial development frameworks through appropriate zoning, location, space management and regulatory policies. While adequate provisions are made for smooth running of formal sector activities, consideration should also be made for the same opportunities for the informal sector. The apathy of public policy makers and urban planners concerning the sector activities contradicts its relevance to societal virtues as it has wide range of implications - be it economic, spatial, environmental and social.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Urban planning issues caused by the activities of the informal sector have endured over the years and are causing serious nuisance to countries that are alien to contemporary planning tackles and techniques (Jelili & Adedibu, 2006). These challenges to urban planning process manifest in various forms found in economic, spatial, environmental, and social aspects. The economics manifestations are in cutting-edge ways, and one critical area is in the decline of infrastructural base. Onibokun (2019) explains this by arguing that “as urban populations grow, and as available resources decline, public infrastructure is being degraded and cities are seriously losing their capacity to operate as productive entities; and that not only is little new infrastructures constructed, but existing infrastructures are poorly maintained. The illegal connections of electricity by the informal sector operators to facilitate their operations result in a drop of electricity voltage, power outages, and transformer vandalization. These circumstances have had effects on the productivity of the economy, resulting in degrading the quality of life in the city. The inadequate provision of infrastructural services and the associated problems has affected most business firms as they spend more of their capital outlay on

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providing their own infrastructures — electricity, water supply, transport, telecommunications, and waste disposal which, under normal circumstances should have been by the urban planning authorities. This, by extension, adds to the costs of production which are passed on to the consumers. These issues make these enterprises not to grow at a rate that would generate enough employment opportunities to meet the demand of the growing population, while fewer and new firms are unable to get started thereby keeping unemployment on a high. High population growth with influx of people will definitely increase cost of living in urban environment. The spatial manifestation in land use planning is found where the locations of facilities are distorted. A particular and highly visible category of this is the siting of automobile workshops. Such issues as distribution, types, reasons for their location, specific impacts, and effective frameworks for the control and/or planning of informal workshops in urban environments before it is scattered everywhere are the issues to be addressed in this regard; and also avoid the growth of squatter settlements or slum areas in urban environments. These automobile workshops sometimes do make deliberate releases or disposals of petrol, diesel, solvents, grease, and lubricants on the environment, thus causing pollution. Bassuer (2018) opines that chemicals such as refrigerator gases used in vehicle air conditioners, and often released during maintenance work at these workshops, are made up of chlorofluoro-carbon, which is capable of depleting the ozone layer and causing a greenhouse effect. This aligns with the conclusion of pollution axiom (2010) that automobile workshops emit large quantities of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and substances known as mobile source air toxics (MSATs) such as benzene, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, 1-butadiene, and lead, among others. Urban planners therefore, need to keep pace with rapid urban growth and make provision for a wide range of contingencies to avoid wide spread illegal, unhealthy and informal developments. Of particular concern is this issue of environmental pollution, which needs to be analysed for effective control and physical planning purposes.

According to Elekwa (2018), many development projects carried out in these areas were without regard to the environmental impact assessment and this poses potential health problems and other hazards such as flooding, congestion, epidemic spread, etc. This has hindered the proper planning of solid waste collection and suitable sanitation arrangements and road networks services and even water and electricity distribution and extension services. Urban residents suffer to a great extent from severe

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environmental and health challenges associated with insufficient access, to clean drinking water, inadequate sewage facilities, and solid waste disposal (United Nations, 2003). Urban roads have declined into marshes in rainy seasons due to careless disposal of waste by the operators in the sector even as more and more people are obliged to live in *unserviced* plots. Stern (1991) confirms this by stating that solid wastes are uncollected and piles of decaying wastes are allowed to rot in the streets. The increasing urban activities and population explosion have resulted in widespread clearing of vegetation covering farmlands and wood lands throughout the area, and erosion has become the greatest menace to the livelihood of city dwellers. Social activities in recreational centres seems to be moribund as such facilities have been taken over by informal activities of road side vendors, drinking spots, small market stalls, and shops of various kinds. With this, public telephone has become an impossible dream; public transport systems are non-existent, and where available, have become severely over loaded.

1.3 The Objective of the Study

While the broad objective of this study is to examine the extent to which informal sector activities pose as a challenge to urban planning in Akwa Ibom State, the specific objectives include:

- I. to investigate urban planning implications of the location and growth of informal sector activities in Akwa Ibom State;
- ii. to examine the challenges informal sector activities pose on urban planning control and system in Akwa Ibom State;
- iii. to investigate whether urban planners do consider informal sector activities in the urban planning process in Akwa Ibom State.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1 The Informal Sector

The informal sector in an economy can be seen in terms of lack of governmental regulations or of institutions that provide job security and benefits. It is seen to form the largest part of the developing countries' economies which basis is in small scale individual entrepreneurship not having the privilege of enjoying the benefit of official

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support or services. Sethuraman (1976) sees the sector to comprise of firms not employing up to ten workers. The sector activities include a wide range of actions from household to personal services and from commercial to non – commercial services. The International Labour Organization (2017) states the forms of such enterprises as embracing easy entry and exit of the business; dependence on indigenous resources; family ownership initiatives; small scale of operation; labour intensive and espoused technology; petty skills required; unregulated, uncontrolled with a competitive market outlook and given no legal or government recognition. The group also include small scale productive, retail and service enterprises such as shoe making and repairs, hair dressing and barbing; mechanical works, carpentry and upholstery; hawkers, street traders; food vendors and a host of others which dot the urban landscape.

Rogerson (2016) distinguishes them into two major categories - the ‘survivalist enterprises’ and the ‘microenterprises’ or ‘growth enterprises’. The first represents activities undertaken by people unable to gain regular wage employment or access to an economic sector of their choice. The majority of operators here tend to be women and they often fall short of a minimum standard of earnings though with petite initial capital investment and no much skill required (Liedholm and Mcpherson, 2019). Theirs is just to overcome poverty and survival is the prime defining feature of these enterprises. The second category which sometimes are very small businesses often involve only the owner, some family members and at most, one to four paid employees. They lack the frills of formality such as business licenses, formal premises, operating permits and accounting procedures, and most have only a limited capital base and their operations have only fundamental business skills. In studying the process of involvement in the informal sector activities, Todaro and Harris’s (2016) models of rural – urban migration view absorption into the labour market as a two-stage process in which an unskilled worker migrates to the city, spends sometime in the ‘urban traditional sector’ till succour in finding modern sector employment.

Simeone (2017) indicated that the sector provides tens of jobs for every one provided by formal sector. But according to Chen (2001), more informal workers or industrial outworkers contribute more to global trade than other sectors of the informal economy. Accordingly, she hangs on that these workers comprise a significant share of the workforce in key export industries, particularly those involving simple manual tasks such as labour–intensive operations, simple machine or potable technology as found in

the textile, garments, and footwear industry. The informal sector is estimated to account for about 75 per cent of the total employment in sub-Saharan Africa, with Nigeria accounting for about a third of the 50 million labour force out of 123.9 million people in 2019.

Simon (2018) notes that the main economic activity in the informal economy is retail trade and most workers in this sector run front shops, stalls, kiosks or hawk goods as part or full-time activity (Oyerinde, 2021). According to Okeke (2000), poverty is seen as the major factor of these informal activities while others such as rural-urban migration, increase in population growth rate, urbanization and unemployment are also crucial contributing factors. In addition, economic crises such as underemployment, lack of governmental resources for basic services, and ineffective and cumbersome government regulations have further fuelled the situation (Urban Age, 2022). Nevertheless, those employed full-time in the formal sector are also forced to find additional means of income to survive due to low salary payments while the unemployed take to any form of job just to make ends meet. Manning (2019) acclaimed also that there is a progressive weakening of the formal economy due to an alarming decrease in its capacity to absorb new entrants to the labour market; hence, entrepreneurs are only in the informal economy 'out of necessity rather than choice'. He concluded that low labour absorption in the formal economy and the dire crisis of survival are the primary factors responsible for the massive expansion of the informal economy that has taken place over the last decade. Recognizing the activities of these informal sectors as one of the important underlying causes of environmental degradation, calls for legal and institutional frameworks that are effective for the sound urban landscape management if cities and towns are to remain both economically and environmentally sustainable.

2.1.2 Environmental Management, Informal Land Use and Planning

The handling of the bio-physical environment and the built or cultural environment to include the control of human activities is the focus in land use and environmental management. Human activities are spatially expressed as land use even as Essaghah (2017) sees it as the use to which land is put. The procedural activities mated in caring and improving the human environment to safeguard air, water, land, and even forest and wildlife, with the aim of protecting and improving quality of human life is another

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perspective to environmental management. According to Uchegbu (2018), it is the shaping of items of environmental nature such that man's penetration and exploitation activities do not affect the environment adversely. However, one of the most disturbing problems of land use in urban areas is its classification (Jelili and Adedibu, 2006). This arises from the flexibility in the factors which produce land use pattern, and more importantly, due to the emerging dichotomy of formal and informal dimensions of land use. Land use planning, which deals with the spatial ordering of human activities in a way to achieve harmony, economy and beauty and is to help solve the conflict brought about by the emergence of informal land use, which does not seem to conform to land use pattern. This is because the process of land use planning ought to have classified all human activities into different primary (residential, commercial, industrial, etc.) and secondary (residential density areas, classes of commercial use, types of industries, etc.) uses before distributing them accordingly in space. This implies that informal land use is a complex land use terminology, which refers to all forms of land use not recognized by the existing formal plan or other legal documents. Interestingly, however, many human activities in developing countries are under this category.

The UNDP (2016) ascribes them as activities that "thrive in their thousands in the cities of the less developed countries, transforming them into hives of tiny enterprises all of which are pitched in stiff competition for dwindling space and patronage". Automobile workshops are repair and maintenance shops for automobiles and they affect repairs in things like brakes, muffler and exhaust systems; electrification in the autos, air-conditioner, glass; and general engine repairs and reinstallation, etc. (Kayemuddin and Kayum, 2013). Most of them are located at undesignated places, unregistered and pay nothing as company tax; make use mostly of artisans and technicians and unstable apprentice. So, instead of making these sets continue the problem of distortion of land use plan and consequently heighten the problem of environmental management, there is need for effective ways of integrating them into formal land use planning and environmental management system.

2.1.3 Urban Land Use Management

It can be adduced that traditional land settlements were mainly founded within the fringe of palaces of traditional rulers for efficient communal interaction. The development and control of the total environment was the joint administrative responsibility of the entire

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community. The tradition settlements were structured according to the local customs and practice; the traditional land tenure system; the agrarian nature of the economy and the existing mode of transportation in most developing countries. Communal lands were also vested in traditional rulers or community leaders in these environments whereas there were some form of family lands which were vested in the hands of various family heads whose legal status were likened to that of a trustee – beneficiary and can allocate, re-allocate and supervise land use. With the institutionalisation of colonial administration in English speaking West African countries, the traditional settlement development approaches slowly gave in to the colonial administration approaches such that in Nigeria, there was the annexation of Lagos as a British colony under the treaty of cession in 1861 and the consequential promulgation in Lagos in 1863 of the Town Improvement Ordinance to control development and urban sanitation (NITP, 1993). The Lord Lugard – led colonial administration made a land proclamation in respect to title of land in northern Nigeria and with the introduction of indirect rule, they constituted the main barrage of change in land administration and settlement development in the English-speaking West African countries. The policy of indirect rule empowered urban settlements to be administered by native rulers or chiefs within their enclave, while the colonial administration gave the European and government reservation areas to develop and create pursuant to the land proclamation act of 1904 to be administered by the colonialists. Different planning standards were specified for the various segments of the cities with physical planning and infrastructure provision concentrated in the European or Government Reservation.

2.2 Review of Theoretical Literature

The literature on informal sector traces the term to the mid-1950s when Arthur, W. Lewis developed a theoretical model of economic development based on the assumption that there was an unlimited supply of labour in most developing countries and that this vast pool of surplus labour would be absorbed as the modern industrial sector as these countries grew. It was then therefore, assumed that the traditional sector comprised petty traders, small-scale producers and a range of casual jobs, and would eventually be absorbed into the formal economy before it subsequently goes. On the contrary however, the International Labour Organization (ILO) and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) undertook a global search for ways and means to

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create more employment for millions of job seekers in cities of developing countries. These were followed up to the creation of the World Employment Programme of the ILO in 1969. Since then, the informal sector has been studied from various angles according to respective needs. Some authors have it that the sector is a helpful analytical mode for studying the nature of segmentation or duality in the urban labour market (Piore 1983; Mazumdar 1983; Amin 1982). Some others have assessed the efficiency of the sector as a tool for urban poverty alleviation (Harriss 1989). The sector has also been studied from an urban planning perspective (Amin 1992; Harper 1992, 1996). Attention on the sector has, however, been drawn to what the ILO calls the “decent work” perspective which has led to a search for ways and means to bring work in the informal sector up to the standards of decent work (Amin 2002). Another perspective is the Urban Environmental Management (UEM) literature which is relatively young, and has started to grow only in the last decade. The ILO finds that the sector is a possible means of urban absorption of rural migrants. The World Bank, in their work, had that urban policy agenda for the 1990s influenced the search for a new paradigm that would move the issue beyond housing and residential infrastructure paradigms, and it emphasized on increasing the productivity of the urban economy and the need to alleviate constraints on productivity; increasing the productivity of the urban poor by increasing demand for labour and improving access to basic infrastructure and social services; and reversing the deterioration of the urban environment (World Bank 1991, 3).

Nevertheless, a theory on ‘systems’ established that the urbanization of cities inter-depend on urban planning which requires integration of insights from the natural, engineering, social and health sciences as well as an active dialogue between the scientists and policy makers (Ruth 2006: 17). The system theory can therefore be used to make the necessary theoretical foundation. The system approach was first developed in the biological and engineering sciences before it was adopted by social scientists in explaining social and organizational phenomena. The major concepts involved in the system model can be summarized thus: (a) a system can be perceived as a whole, with its parts in inter-dependent relationship. (b) a system has its boundaries and can be viewed in terms of its relationship with other systems. (c) Systems have sub-systems, and are a part of a supra system. (d) A system can be regarded as either open or closed. In this case, cities or urban areas are seen as open systems, interacting with other systems.

The system theory is both relevant and appropriate to the study of sustainable

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urban planning and infrastructure because it provides a flexible framework; one responsive to the issues of scale, and changing social and environmental conditions precipitated by the urbanization of urban areas overtime. The system theory sees urban areas as emergent phenomena embedded within a spatial and historical context of interacting processes. It sees urban areas (cities) as complex, evolving social systems that react and interact in unexpectedly complex ways to seemingly simple changes. Based on this, the urban area is seen as an on-going, ever-changing, primarily social system, comprising human activities and their inter-relationships with the flows of people, materials, and energy. The theory highlights the interdependence of the ultimate physical limits placed on urban services and infrastructure and the rate of urban growth. This approach naturally lends itself to defining hierarchical systems, which are characterized by urban elements, interacting horizontally with each other and vertically with larger organizing structures. In other words, urban areas can be characterised as open systems that inter-depend on the rural areas, or be more influenced by a larger network of other urban areas (Kay et al 1999:721, 1994:32; Ausubel, 1988: 3). The urban systems are self-organizing and can be thought of in terms of resilience (adaptability) and transformability (ability to fundamentally change state).

Applying this theory to this study will help explain the forces that drive urban infrastructural development. Urban planning and infrastructure are linked to the spatial and usage patterns that impact human ecological processes. These processes influence more micro level phenomenon, such as human behaviour and activity which serve as feed back into landscape and social patterns in the urban area. Completing the loop, acknowledgement of change spurs policy development which acts as factors affecting further alterations of urban infrastructure. Therefore, planning decisions to extend urban services to meet the fast growing spread of development in the urban areas will precipitate demands on infrastructural facilities necessary to deliver and sustain it. The pictogram below captures the framework used in this paper.

Figure 1: A System Approach to Urban Planning and Development.

By the early 1970s, a new concept of environmentalism had emerged (Mikesell, 1974). It states that the man-nature relationship is not a one-way affair. Man affects his environment as he responds to the changing conditions set by the environment, and the environment responds to human manipulation, thereby creating a state of dynamic equilibrium that continues to adjust and readjust in space and time (Olofin, 1989). The term 'environment' defies any rigid definition. Ofomata (1976), however, presented a broad view of the environment as consisting of the realm of nature, the realm of man, and the realm of nature and man. The Chicago school avers that urban planning and social intervention agencies are institutions that may give a proper direction and it is best known for applying the principles of ecology to develop the Social Disorganization Theory. It is recognized that urban expansion was not haphazard but quite strongly controlled by community-level forces such as land values, zoning ordinances, landscape features, circulation corridors, and historical contingency. This was characterized as ecological because the external factors were neither chance nor

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intended, but rather arose from the natural forces in the environment which limit adaptive spatial and temporal relationships between individuals. Obadan et al. (1996) refer to informal economic activities as the informal sector, and Lubell (1991) refers to it as micro- enterprises. For a study that wants to analyze the informal economic activities of urban areas and their impact on the environment, the informal sector concept provides a very useful framework. However, in this study, the operational definition of the informal sector will be “all income - generating activities with the exclusion of those that involve contractual and legally regulated employment”. It usually comprises manufacturing, service/repair and trade (small scale distribution) activities which affect the environment both positively and negatively with their by products. Adeyinka et al. (2006) on a study in Nigeria, observed the lack of official recognition of urban informal activities in the management of urban spaces and provision of basic infrastructure and services with the consequence of them spilling into any available space and location, thereby contributing significantly to disorderliness and chaotic circumstances in such environment.

Asuquo et al. (2022) argue that the unemployed in any economy will seek all available means of survival and possibly the only destination is the informal economy, where they operate as self-employed, hawkers, wage earners, scavengers, shop-owners, shop-keepers and several other activities unregulated by the State. Policy issues and debates opinions differ widely on what should be the appropriate attitudes and policies toward the informal sector. Some of the more optimistic advocates of the sector tend to (as a form of popular development), a vital source of employment and income for the poor, the seedbed of local entrepreneurship, and a potent instrument in the campaign to combat poverty and social exclusion. They dismiss earlier characterizations of the sector as easy to enter and requiring little money and skills, which led to the misconception that the informal sector required no form of official support. They also condemn the large number of regulations and bureaucratic procedures from the different institutions and levels of government which tend to stifle entrepreneurship, and to inhibit the realization of the full potential of the informal sector. On the other hand, others see the sector as an incongruity, a source of syndrome, and an obstacle to the development of a modern economy. They condemn the slums, health risks, insecurity, and exploitation associated with the sector, and hope that like other transitory phases in the course of development, the informal sector will wither away with time and economic progress. Even those who idealize the sector recognize that it is at best a mixed blessing.

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These uncertainties about the informal sector are part of the age-long debates about the rural and urban paths to development, and doubts about whether urbanization in general is harmful or beneficial. The argument suggests that the allocation of national resources is usually skewed disproportionately in favour of the urban areas. It is said that if conditions in rapidly developing cities continue to be improved, more and more people will be attracted to them to aggravate the problems of unemployment and squalor; that the worsening health and environmental problems of cities are caused by the unregulated activities of the informal sector, which, if allowed to continue, could make cities uncomfortable and unsustainable to live for present and future generations. Until recently the concern for environmental protection in most developing countries environment has tended to focus on non-urban issues such as desertification, soil erosion, oil spillage, dumping of hazardous wastes, etc., giving only scant and largely negative attention to the worsening deficiencies in housing, water supply, sanitation, pollution, waste management, food safety, security, and other issues which directly affect public health and welfare. Recent research suggests that the path to urban sustainability is in building and managing more inclusive and socially equitable cities which involve the continuous review of legislative and administrative activities in order to cater for the informal sector activities; improve security of land and housing infrastructure for the urban poor; upgrade slums, and strengthen urban local governance through broad-based partnerships that take the needs and participation of the informal sector fully into account.

3.1 Methodology

The research design used in this study is the survey method normally adopted and very useful in opinion studies to capture the necessary arguments relating to the study and the study area. Interviews were conducted to the residents of the State based on the three Senatorial Districts. Two local government areas were chosen from each senatorial district from which two villages were also chosen not on any particular sampling technique but of purposive and accidental sampling format. The residents which form the population of study consist of farmers, fishermen, welders, carpenters, traders, (provision stores/sellers in local markets and roadside), craftsmen, tailors/seamstress, liquor/beer shops, mechanics and hunters, and any trade that could be so classified as under the informal sector within the State as well as urban planners in Ministry of Urban

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Planning and Development, Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA) staff, and various urban planners in the sampled local government areas.

The artisans were estimated at about 800,000 while the ministries staff and other urban planners were estimated at about 600. Such levels of people were chosen as they are seen to understand and appreciate the intricacies of the sector challenges and how their activities are being influenced by the informal sector activities on one side, and urban authorities in their plan framework on the other side. Other sources of information included secondary sources which were from textbooks and relevant journals for the literature. The survey involved the use of unstructured interview. With the total population estimated at 800,600, the sample size is thus drawn therewith. Using a table of random numbers, the sample size for the study was determined using the formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = present population

N = finite population

e = the level of significance (0.05)

The population of the study is therefore projected to be 390,000, using the formula:

$$P_t = \frac{P_t(1+r)^n}{100}$$

Where:

P_o = projected population

P_t = population of the base year

r = rate of growth (2.3)

n = 4 years.

Applying the formula $P_o = \frac{800,600(1+2.3)^4}{100}$

gave a projected population of 390,000 persons for the study. This value was then substituted in the Yamane formula as:

$$n = \frac{800,600}{1 + 800,600(0.0025)}$$

This gave the sample size of about 2,000 people to be interviewed for the study.

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The target population was the top and middle management staff of AKSEPWMA and other urban planners within the ministries and local government areas. This was done to authenticate and balance the information gathered from the informal sector operators. Selection was done by random sampling to have a fair representation of the people interviewed. The random sampling method gave the respondents the opportunities of being equally represented. The table below shows our sample distribution.

Table 3.1 Sample Distributions

Sample size	2,000				
Gender distribution	1,250 males		750 females		
Age distribution	Under 20yrs	21-30 yrs.	31-40 yrs.	41-50 yrs.	50 & above
Work/Occupation	800 mechanics/traders/fishermen	500 liquor./beer shops/welders	150 AKSEPWMA staff members	250 ministries staff/local govt. areas urban planners	300 others
Marital status	900 respondents were married		1100 respondents were single		

Source: Author's Compilation, 2023

Using a table of random numbers, the sample size for the study was about 2,000 interviewees. In any case, demographic information of the interviewees were also sorted and this included sex, age, occupational distribution, and marital status

Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Presentation of Responses from Interview Conducted

Based on the objectives of this study, certain questions were asked to draw the attention and accommodate the views of the various respondents that would give appropriate responses on the subject. Objective one was to investigate urban planning implications of the location and growth of informal sector activities in Akwa Ibom State.

Objective two was to examine the challenges informal sector activities pose on urban planning control and system in Akwa Ibom State.

Objective three was to investigate whether urban planners do consider informal sector activities in the urban planning process in Akwa Ibom State.

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4.2 Findings

From the Nigerian 1999 constitution, town planning activities is resided in the State governments. The local governments' functions to establish and manage markets, collect and dispose waste, manage motor parks and so on. But from findings, the officials said that due to poor funding and lack of qualified human resource, the Ministry of Lands, Survey and Town Planning, and the local government's works department had not been able to do much in terms of urban planning and management and the regulation of informal activities. As the state has grown over the last 22 years, there had been a high demand for space and land for residential development, commercial activities and other uses. With the failure of public control and management, the private market had become the main provider of land to prospective developers and the driver of the local economy. Haphazard location of informal activities, petty trading, cottage industries, and services have become the order of the day. Economic activities and land use lack adequate management and therefore, as this study has shown, lead to many challenges and problems, which if not addressed, will in the future lead to more complex environmental problems and public health hazards. For basic infrastructure and services to lack, no investor would be attracted to the State to stimulate local economic opportunities. The Federal Government of Nigeria in 2012 approved the sum of N200 billion for the operation of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Credit Guarantee Scheme (SMEDAN, 2013). Such grants/loans have not reached the informal operators as their activities are not accountable. An unplanned system cannot support sustained development that leads to healthy economic growth, enhanced welfare of the poor urban residents, and the attainment of the New Urban Agenda.

5. Conclusion

The study has provided insight into the nature and characteristics of informal activities as well as the physical planning implications of informal sector activities in Akwa Ibom State. The capacity of the informal sector economy to provide employment to the teeming urban population cannot be underscored. However, the sector poses considerable challenges to urban planners not only in the State in view, but also in other States of the federation on how to integrate them into the urban system where the level of application of physical planning principle and practice will manage and regulate their activities. The environmental and public health challenges that they pose have been left

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unaddressed by planners and other stakeholders. There is need for urban planners to understand the needs and dynamics of the informal sector as the driver of local economic development and work assiduously with all relevant players in the economy to integrate them in the spatial planning framework in order to promote economic development and growth that is sensitive to environmental quality and health of the urban residents. This will help to ensure economic development while promoting environmental health and social harmony in urban centres. Following these recommendations, the issue of demolition of illegal outlets should not be contemplated as demolition is extremely costly when the informal constructions represent solid investments and are a vital part of the economy. Informality is seen as a response to inefficiency of a state's responsibility related to good land administration and urban management, or to economic development and provision of job opportunities.

However, the state considers that as urban growth rate is high (particularly in developing countries), comprehensive spatial planning is essential to regenerate the areas affected by informal developments and impose controls on development with strict legalization.

Recommendations

To address the challenges and problems that informal land use activities pose in Akwa Ibom State, the following recommendations are made:

- a. The urban planning system should understand and promote the informal sector to enhance and boost local economic development by providing suitable sites and locations serviced with basic infrastructure that are accessible and safe for them to thrive.
- b. An urban master plan should be prepared by the State, with technical and financial assistance to provide a framework for the growth and development. The plan should propose clusters for the location of informal sector activities, integrated and blended with other land uses like residential, institutional, etc; and make broad design suggestions that enhance the built fabric of the State. There is need to rationalise the locations of informal activities. Those exposed to higher levels of danger, hazards and risks should be relocated to safer and more secure sites. This applies also to activities along busy major roads.
- c. The State government should address their needs in term of access to

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infrastructure - power, water, safety, waste collection and disposal; sanitary facilities and security and make less cumbersome forms of registration of informal activities; with affordable rates/levies/taxation to enable them survive in the current climate of economic recession in the country.

- d. Enforcement of minimum environmental standards such as public health and sanitation guidelines, business operation hours, etc., should be negotiated and agreed with informal operators so that they are acceptable and adhered to.

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